

Cytochrome P450 Enzymes : Significance, Multiplicity of Isoforms, Substrates, Catalytic and Regulatory Mechanisms, Physiological Functions and Clinical Correlations†

RAMESH CHANDRA^{a*} and RITU ANEJA^b

^aDr. B. R. Ambedkar Center for Biomedical Research, ^bDepartment of Chemistry, University of Delhi, Delhi-110 007

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Historically there has been considerable interest in comparing patterns of biotransformation of xenobiotic chemicals in experimental animal models and humans, e.g. in areas such as drug metabolism and chemical carcinogenesis. With the availability of more basic knowledge it has become possible to attribute the oxidation of selected chemicals to individual cytochrome P450 enzymes in animals and humans. Further, these cytochrome P450 enzymes can be characterized by their classification into distinct subfamilies, which are defined as having >59% amino acid sequence homology. The cytochrome P450 (P450) enzymes are present throughout most of the phylogenetic spectrum. P450s are involved in the oxidation of other compounds normally found in vertebrates or 'endobiotics', e.g. fat-soluble vitamins, fatty acids, eicosanoids, and even alkaloids. However, most of the liver microsomal P450s oxidize a wide variety of substrates and have the function of removing natural products (ingested in food-stuff) from the body. In support of this view, the levels of many of these P450s vary dramatically among humans, as opposed to the levels of steroidogenic P450s, which are tightly regulated. Cytochrome P450s also function in critical roles in the synthesis of some steroids, and loss of function can be debilitating or lethal. Well over 500 P450s have now been characterized at the level of their DNA sequences. Quoting this number is somewhat misleading, because the number of P450s in a single species is probably no higher than 40-50, at least at our current state of knowledge. The 'total' number of cytochrome P450s will probably grow very large with more information about P450s in insects, plants, bacteria and vertebrate species that have not yet been examined in detail.

Every day we consume carbohydrates, proteins and fats. These bulk nutrients are catabolized in a very orderly fashion, using very efficient convergent pathways, to fulfill energy needs of the body and to produce precursor molecules for anabolism. It is not commonly appreciated that, in addition to the essential nutrients, we also ingest inadvertently many xenobiotics such as plant secondary metabolites, prescription drugs and environmental pollutants. Many of these foreign substances are toxic. Nature with admirable foresight, has designed special oxidative pathways for elimination of these toxins from the body. Without these pathways our bodies will stop functioning as we will be replete with all types of unwanted hazardous chemicals.

Oxygenases, particularly cytochrome P450, play an important role in the oxidation of xenobiotics into water-soluble products suitable for excretion¹. Among numerous foreign chemicals handled by cytochrome P450 enzymes, the ones that stand out as typical are benzo[α]pyrene found in tobacco smoke and charcoal broiled meat; polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) now banned, but previously used in electrical transformers and dioxin, a by-product of the production of the commonly used defoliant. In fact, cytochrome P450s complement the immune system to protect our bodies against foreign chemicals.

It is noteworthy that cytochrome P450 oxygenases also play a very important role in multienzyme systems responsible for the synthesis of steroids, fat-soluble vitamins, fatty

acids, eicosanoids etc.^{2,3}. Cytochrome P450s are, therefore, very versatile biocatalysts. Any defects or alterations in the synthesis of P450 cytochromes in humans are expected to generate serious health problems.

Classification and nomenclature

Cytochrome P450 is the family name of closely related oxygenases, which have got overlapping substrate and inducer specificity. Intricately folded polypeptide chains of these enzymes harbor an iron-protoporphyrin IX molecule (also called heme) as the prosthetic group. Iron, in the ionic form is held in the center of the porphyrin ring by four-coordination bonds with the nitrogen atoms of the tetrapyrrole ring. Fifth axial coordination position of iron is occupied by the ionized sulfhydryl group of the amino acid residue cysteine. In the reduced Fe²⁺ form, the sixth coordination position of iron, binds oxygen although this site can also capture carbon monoxide with very high affinity. Carbon monoxide complex of all cytochrome oxygenases exhibits λ_{max} around 450 nm in their optical spectra. This observation accounts for the origin of the term P450 in the family name of these cytochromes. The nomenclature committee of the International Union of Biochemistry has given them the formal designation, hemothiolate protein P450 on the basis of their common structural features⁴.

It should be noted that cytochrome P450 family of enzymes is not related functionally or by evolution to cyto-

†Dedicated to Professor Sukh Dev on the occasion of his 75th. birth anniversary.

chromes a, b and c present in the respiratory chain of mitochondria. The major difference between the two classes of cytochromes is that the former transfers electrons to oxygen, whereas respiratory cytochromes transfer electrons to other proteins.

Evolution and divergence of cytochrome P450

In the early work on purification of P450s, individual proteins were given trivial names that were often related to the inducer, the wavelength maximum of the ferrous-CO complex, the order of elution from a column, an artificial substrate, etc.⁵. A systematic nomenclature was developed based upon the similarity of primary sequences. This system has been revised several times⁶ and is now most readily available. The basis of the classification is that the first number designates the 'family'. In general, a 40% sequence identity is the cutoff. A 59% sequence identity is needed to put two P450s in the same subfamily, designated with a letter. There are some exceptions to both rules. The final number indicates a particular P450, but this is not used when the P450 is considered to be more conserved among species (e.g. rat and human P450 1A2). This point is somewhat arbitrary, of course.

The systematic nomenclature is based upon sequence alignments without regard to function. Comparisons of catalytic activities can be and have been made at several levels of increasing complexity. (i) Allelic variants and site-directed mutagenesis products of a single P450. In this case the number of residues that vary is small (<10, often 1). (ii) Within a P450 subfamily. For instance, P450s 1A1 and 1A2 are compared. (iii) Among animal species. For instance, one can compare activities of rat P450 1A1 with human P450 1A1. (iv) Among all P450s. In essence this is what one does when modeling the interaction of a P450 with its substrate/product using distantly related P450 structures, e.g. bacterial 3-dimensional structures developed from X-ray crystallography.

P450 1A1 :

P450 1A1 is considered by some to be 'ancient' P450⁷. The enzyme has been purified from rats, rabbits and mice. The human enzyme has never been completely purified from tissue in a fully catalytically active form but has been expressed in several heterologous systems⁸. This P450 has catalytic activity in the oxidation of polycyclic hydrocarbons, regardless of the species of origin, and these activities have been the focus of much attention. All of the enzymes examined to date also seem to be reasonable catalysts for 7-ethoxyresorufin-*O*-deethylation, and this activity is often used as a convenient marker⁹.

Although P450 1A1 is generally considered to be an 'aryl hydrocarbon hydroxylase' several lines of investiga-

tion suggest that the rates of oxidation of the prototypic substrate benzo[α]pyrene are considerably less with human P450 1A1 (at least the recombinant products) than rat P450 1A1. Another difference is seen with warfarin oxidation. Rat P450 1A1 primarily hydroxylates (*R*)-warfarin at the 6- and 8-positions, while mouse P450 1A1 has no real activity.

P450 1A2 :

P450 1A2 has been purified from rats, rabbits, mice and humans. A number of expression systems have developed. The rat and human enzymes are 75% identical in amino acid sequence¹⁰.

These proteins are usually isolated predominantly in the high-spin iron configuration. They all have 7-ethoxyresorufin-*O*-deethylation, acetanilide-4-hydroxylation, and phenacetin-*O*-deethylation activities and can catalyse the *N*-hydroxylation of numerous heterocyclic amines¹¹.

P450 2A :

P450 2A subfamily proteins have been studied in mouse, rabbit, rat, human, monkey and hamster. The proteins differ markedly in catalytic specificity, despite their sequence similarity. It was first in the 2A subfamily that substitution at a single amino acid residue was shown to change the catalytic specificity of a P450. Mouse P450s 2a4 and 2a5 differ in only 11 amino acids. The substitution F209L converted P450 2a5 from a coumarin 7-hydroxylase to a steroid 15 α -hydroxylase¹². Other residues found to be critical to P450 2a5 activity were (Val) 117, (Met) 365, and (Ala) 481. Further, changing residue 209 from Phe to Asn converted the preferred substrate (for 15 α -hydroxylation) from deoxycorticosterone to corticosterone. Other substitutions at 209 and 481 influenced the regioselectivity of androstenedione and dehydroepiandrosterone hydroxylation¹³.

P450 2B :

The existence of closely related rat P450 2B subfamily proteins has been known for many years. Rat P450s 2B1 and 2B2 were found to differ in only 14 residues¹⁴. In general, P450 2B2 catalyzes the same reactions as P450 2B1 but at lower rates. However, some exceptions have been reported in the literature over the years and it is likely that more examples of catalytic selectivity of the two enzymes may be found as detailed structures, function studies are carried out.

P450 2C :

The P450 2C subfamily has been studied extensively in humans and rabbits. In all species examined, this is a complex subfamily consisting of many closely related proteins that can differ markedly in function. In humans, at least four P450s are found (2C8, 2C9, 2C18, 2C19), although Southern hybridization analysis suggests that there

may be more genes (some might be pseudogenes) and the possibility that 2C10 is a separate gene cannot be ruled out at this time¹⁵. All of the human P450 2C subfamily members are >80% identical in their amino acid sequences. P450 2C9 and 2C19 have tolbutamide methyl hydroxylation activity, P450 2C9 has (*S*)-warfarin 7-hydroxylation activity, and P450 2C19 is the classic (*S*)-mephenytoin-4'-hydroxylase.

P450 2D :

The enzyme now known as P450 2D6 attracted attention because of its role as the polymorphic debrisoquinone 4-hydroxylase in human. In human, the other P450 2D subfamily members are only pseudogenes. In rats, there are four P450 2D genes, 2D1, 2D2, 2D3, and 2D4. Other P450 2D subfamily enzymes have been studied in other species. The rat P450 2D subfamily enzymes have not been studied in great detail. However, it is known for many years that rat P450 2D activities are sensitive to inhibition by quinine whereas human P450 2D6 is sensitive to a stereoisomer, quinidine.

A number of site-directed mutagenesis studies done on P450 2D6, indicate the significance of several residues. Asp301 is suggested to be anionic residue responsible for binding positively charged substrates and inhibitors in the active site, because mutation of this residue to a neutral residue lowered the apparent affinity for quinidine and attenuated catalytic activity.

An interesting P450 2D1 mutation is 1380F. This had the effect of modifying catalytic activity towards one substrate (bufuralol) but not another (debrisoquine). An allelic variant (residue 374) in P450 2D6 has been identified. The two proteins have altered stereoselectivity in the oxidation of metoprolol.

P450 2E :

P450 2E1 has been purified from rats, rabbits and human. The amino acid sequence similarity of these enzymes is ~80%. P450 2E1, from all species, catalyzes the oxidation of ethanol and other alcohols, short chain alkyl *N*-nitrosamines, and many low molecular weight organic solvents, some of which are of interest as cancer suspect agents. No major qualitative differences among P450 2E1 enzymes isolated from various sources have been detected to date, but rates of catalysis have not been strictly compared in many cases. Relatively little has been done regarding the effects of site-directed mutagenesis.

Most animal species appear to contain only a single P450 2E gene, P450 2E1. However, rabbits also produce P450 2E2 (in the neonatal period), which differs in 16 amino acid residues. A direct comparison of rabbit P450s 2E1 and 2E2 indicated similar patterns but relatively less activity with P450 2E2 for all substrates.

P450 3A :

The evidence now indicates that there are three P450 3A subfamily proteins in human, 3A4, 3A5 and 3A7, with the latter apparently being expressed only in fetal tissue, placenta and possibly tumors¹⁶. In rats, at least four or five P450 3A enzymes are found, 3A1, 3A2, 3A9, 3A18 and 3A23. To date only one rabbit P450 3A enzyme, 3A6, has been reported. In humans, P450 3A4 appears to be the most highly abundant P450 enzyme on the whole, and is probably involved in the oxidation of one-half the drugs prescribed today¹⁶. Obviously, much attention has been given to this P450 and the suitability of prediction of this activity.

P450 17A :

A single gene is found in this subfamily, and the protein only has catalytic activity towards a few steroids. However, considerable differences are seen among the species. All species catalyze 17 α -hydroxylation of progesterone and pregnenolone. The rat, hog, guinea pig, and trout enzymes utilize both 17 α -progesterone and 17 α -hydroxypregnenolone as substrates, forming androstenedione and dehydroepiandrosterone as products. This latter activity is used to term the enzyme a '17,20-lyase'. Human and bovine P450 17A can oxidize 17 α -hydroxypregnenolone but not 17 α -hydroxyprogesterone. Human P450 17A also catalyzes progesterone 16 α -hydroxylation but the bovine enzyme does not, although the two enzymes have 71% amino acid sequence homology.

Occurrence and reactions

Cytochrome family of heme proteins occur ubiquitously in unicellular organisms as well as in higher plants and animals. In mammal, P450 cytochromes are present in all types of cells except mature red blood cells and skeletal muscles. They are found predominantly in endoplasmic reticulum and mitochondria and in greatest abundance in the liver. Types of substances oxygenated by cytochromes P450 are listed in Table 1.

TABLE 1—SUBSTRATES FOR CYTOCHROME P450

Xenobiotics	Physiologically occurring compounds
Drugs, including antibiotics	Steroids
Carcinogens	Eicosanoids
Antioxidants	Fatty acids
Solvents	Lipid hydroperoxides
Anaesthetics	Retinoids
Dyes	Acetone, acetol
Pesticides	
Petroleum products	
Alcohols	
Odorants	

Fig. 1 Systematic representation of monooxygenase system.

Our knowledge on the scope of P450 catalyzed reactions is still incomplete. It is estimated that almost all of the approximately two hundred thousand man-made environment pollutants are potential substrates of these cytochromes. Given the possibility of introduction of new drugs as well as other novel xenobiotics, one cannot put upper limit on the number of compounds acted on by the cytochrome P450 family of enzymes.

Most of the reactions catalyzed by P450 enzymes begin with the transfer of electrons from NADPH to NADP-dependent flavoprotein reductase in the microsomal system or to ferredoxin reductase and a non-heme iron protein in the mitochondrial and bacterial systems¹⁷. From there on electrons are transferred to cytochrome P450 (Fig. 1). The types of transformation¹⁸ catalyzed by P450 oxygenases include hydroxylation, epoxidation, peroxygenation, deamination and dehalogenation as well as reductive dehalogenation. Some of the transformations such as conversion of cholesterol to corticoid and sex hormones are biologically essential, while others, particularly with xenobiotics, lead to the formation of more polar compounds that are more readily excreted directly or after conjugation with water-soluble agents such as glucuronic acid and glutathione^{19,20} (Fig. 2). This is usually a detoxification process, but in some instances foreign compounds are converted to products with much greater cytotoxicity mutagenicity or carcinogenicity.

Some of the P450s especially those involved in steroid transformations, are fairly selective in their choice of substrates, whereas, other P450s, particularly those in liver

Phase-I products :

Phase-II products :

Fig. 2. Detoxification of xenobiotics by Phase-I and Phase-II enzymes

microsomes, have unusually broad and overlapping substrate specificity. It may be noted that most of the substrates accepted by P450 cytochromes are lipophilic in character. However, there is no evidence that charge interactions contribute to the binding of substrate with the active sites of the enzymes.

Reaction types catalysed by cytochromess P450 :

Aliphatic hydroxylation :

Aromatic hydroxylation :

Epoxidation :

Dealkylation reactions :

Deamination :

N-Oxidation reactions :

Sulfoxidation :

Desulfuration :

Dechlorination :

Mechanism of oxygen and peroxide activation

As mentioned earlier, the active site of P450 contains iron-protoporphyrin IX bound in part by hydrophobic forces. The fifth ligand is a thiolate anion provided by a cysteine residue, a feature that contributes to the unusual spectral and catalytic properties of P450, and the sixth coordination position may be occupied by an exchangeable water molecule. Upon reduction of the iron, O₂ (or, in a competitive

fashion CO) can be bound in the sixth position.

Oxygenation reactions catalysed by P450 cytochromes may be represented by the general equation,

In this equation RH is the substrate and NADPH is the initial two electron donor²¹. The equation is the modified form of an earlier version and is in accord with the known stoichiometry of the hydroxylation reaction. The first step in the reaction cycle is substrate binding, which perturbs the spin state equilibrium of the cytochrome and facilitates uptake of the first electron. To initiate the oxidative reactions, O₂ is bound to the ferrous ion of the heme *trans* to thiolate. This intermediate can also be written as the resonance form Fe³⁺ (O²⁻) with the substrate still present (Fig. 3). Transfer of the second electron then occurs, with the possible involvement of cytochrome b₅ as an additional electron donor in mammalian microsomal systems^{22,23}. The next step is not well understood but involves the splitting of the oxygen-oxygen bond with the uptake of two protons at some stage and generation of an activated iron-oxene species, and the release of H₂O. Considering the redox possibilities with the sulfur, iron and oxygen atoms, several resonance forms are possible for the active oxygen intermediate. Oxygen insertion into the substrate is believed to involve hydrogen abstraction from the substrate and recombination of the re-

Fig. 3. Mechanism of hydroxylation by cytochrome P450.

sulting transient hydroxyl and carbon radicals to give the final product. Dissociation of ROH then restores the P450 to the starting ferric state. Also shown in Fig. 3 is the way in which a peroxy compound may substitute for O₂ and reducing equivalents in what is termed the peroxide shunt. Homolytic cleavage is envisioned with the formation of an iron-bound hydroxyl radical and an alkoxy radical (XO') capable of hydrogen abstraction from the substrate. Thus, oxygenation by O₂ and by peroxy compounds has some common mechanistic features.

Functions

There are two general views concerning the biological functions of the cytochrome P450 enzymes. In one view these enzymes are primarily involved in the metabolism of endogenous substances. The other view holds that a major function of the protein is to remove foreign chemicals from the body^{23,24}. There are good examples to support each view. In some instances both the functions appear to be carried out by a single enzyme. For the most part, however, particular enzymes seem to be dedicated to one or the other purpose.

One of the main tasks of some of the P450 enzymes is the metabolism of drugs. Indeed, some recent findings suggest that an individual's response to a particular xenobiotic is partly a consequence of the number of active cytochrome P450 enzymes in the body. In some instances, there may be a 50-fold range in enzyme activity. Such variation is thought to account for the undesirable effects some people experience with standard doses of a particular drug. Approximately in 10% of the total world human population, particular enzymes may be effectively missing. Because these individuals cannot eliminate the substance from their bodies, they continually accumulate it, sometimes with serious consequences.

Cytochrome P4502D6 was discovered in just such an instance by Robert Smith of St. Mary's Hospital Medical School in London. Smith had been participating as a volunteer in a study of the drug, debrisoquine, which reduces blood pressure. The drug produced a greatly exaggerated effect in Smith and he became quite ill. The episode provoked him to investigate the metabolism of the drug. He discovered that cytochrome P4502D6 was involved in clearing the drug from the body and that he was genetically deficient for the enzyme. It is now known that about seven percent of the Caucasian population lack the enzyme. These people experience a number of side-effects because they cannot adequately metabolize debrisoquine and certain other drugs, such as phenformin.

Most of the eukaryotic P450s are considered to be lo-

cated in the endoplasmic reticulum (i.e. microsomal), except for the two P450 11 products in steroidogenic tissues²⁵. These mitochondrial P450s and their bacterial counterparts utilize electron transport systems consisting of a flavoprotein and an iron-sulfur protein (adrenodoxin), instead of the single flavoprotein (containing FMN and FAD) in the endoplasmic reticulum. Further, the mitochondrial and bacterial P450s are usually much more selective in terms of the range of substrates each will oxidize. In recent years, it has been revealed²⁶⁻²⁸ that hepatic P450s are found in mitochondria and have significant catalytic activity towards xenobiotics as well as steroids.

Cytochrome P450 reactions are also extremely important in handling carcinogens. This can be shown by altering the complement of cytochrome P450 enzymes in an experimental animal. The presence or absence of particular enzyme can have dramatic effects (positive or negative) on the formation of tumors in response to a carcinogen. In some cases carcinogens do not cause biological damage unless a particular cytochrome P450 enzyme is present. In these instances the enzymes modify the carcinogens so they become electrophilic (chemically active), allowing the chemicals to covalently interact with DNA to produce mutations. Apart from modifying drugs and carcinogens, cytochrome P450 enzymes are also involved in modifying endogenous substances. One of their most crucial functions is the hydroxylation of steroids, bile acids and certain vitamins (vitamins A and D and their metabolites). The importance of these hydroxylations is evident in certain genetic diseases. For example, about one in 10000 infants has a deficiency in the enzyme cytochrome P45021B. This enzyme hydroxylates the 21st carbon atom in steroids such as pregnenolone and progesterone. The absence of these enzymes can lead to a 'salt-wasting syndrome' which can be fatal.

Endogenous alkaloids are also modified by cytochrome P450 enzymes. For example, alkaloids, codeine and morphine are now known to be synthesized in the brain and a few other tissues. The cytochrome P450 enzymes appear to act as catalysts in the process of synthesizing these substances, including the conversion of codeine to morphine. Another important group of substances, the 20-carbon eicosanoids, are synthesized from arachidonic acid by cytochrome P450 enzymes. This group includes important signaling molecules such as prostaglandins, thromboxanes and leukotrienes. There is considerable interest in the function of eicosanoids and other long-chain fatty acids as messengers and the function of P450s in relation to the metabolism of these compounds. Arachidonic acid is converted to alcohol and to epoxides by P450s²⁸⁻³⁰, and these epoxides can even be incorporated into phospholipids³¹⁻³³. There is

significant evidence that the epoxides of arachidonic acid can exert important physiological responses at low concentration.

It has been shown recently that cytochrome P450 enzymes are involved in the synthesis of the simple gas nitric oxide (NO). In the past few years it has been shown that nitric oxide has several important biological roles, acting as a neurotransmitter, a mediator of blood pressure and a toxin that kills invading pathogens. The two classes of enzymes that synthesize nitric oxide (found in the brain and the immune system's macrophages) consist of two domains. One part of the nitric oxide synthase molecule contains a cytochrome P450 domain, whereas, another part has a reductase domain (containing two flavin molecules). Another example offers a revealing instance of another species' unique dependence on these enzymes. Many plants produce substances that are highly toxic to insects. Among these are plants of *Apiaceae* (carrot and parsley family) and *Rutaceae* (citrus and other aromatic trees) species, which produce xanthotoxin-a molecule that is poisonous to most insects that would eat the plant. There is, however, a species of butterfly that actually prefers to feed on these plants. Larvae of the black swallowtail butterfly (*Papilio polyxenes*) can find a nutritious meal where other species of insect find death. How do these larvae do it? It has been shown that the larvae have a unique response to xanthotoxin. After a larva ingests the leaves of these plants, the larva's midgut produces the enzyme cytochrome P4506B1. The enzyme catalyzes the oxidative destruction of xanthotoxin, allowing the animal to remove the molecule from its system. It appears that xanthotoxin induces the synthesis of the cytochrome P4506B1 enzyme in the larva, thus abetting its own destruction. Other species of insects do not produce this enzyme, and thus cannot digest these plants.

Clinical correlations

Induction of the cytochrome P450 system may result in altered efficacy of therapeutic drugs, as the accelerated rate of hydroxylation will increase the inactivation and/or enhance the excretion rate of drugs. Induction of this protein system may also produce unexpected and unwanted side-effects of therapeutic agents due to increased formation of toxic metabolites that may cause cell injury if produced in large enough concentrations. Clinical problems may develop as a consequence of cytochrome P450 induction.

The increase in the clearance of oral contraceptives by rifampicin, an antituberculosis drug, a CYP3A4 inducer, has been shown to decrease the effectiveness of the contraceptive agent and increase the incidence of pregnancy in women who are prescribed both drugs. Fatalities have been reported in patients who are simultaneously treated with

phenobarbital, a long-active sedative and potent cytochrome P450 inducer, and warfarin, an anticoagulant, which is prescribed to patients with clotting disorders. Higher doses of warfarin are required in these patients to maintain the same effective concentration of the drug to delay coagulation because warfarin is a substrate for the cytochrome P450 induced by phenobarbital³⁴. Consequently, the drug is metabolized and cleared at a faster rate, which reduces its therapeutic efficacy. Clinical problems are created when phenobarbital is removed from the treatment regimen with no corresponding decrease in warfarin levels. With time, cytochrome P450 levels decrease to the noninduced state but the high concentrations of warfarin, proper under conditions of accelerated metabolism and clearance, are in excess and produce unwanted haemorrhage.

Induction of cytochrome CYP2E1 due to chronic alcohol use has led to a warning for consumers of acetaminophen, a common over-the-counter analgesic agent, because this cytochrome P450 will metabolize acetaminophen to a toxic metabolite that may lead to liver cell damage³⁵⁻³⁷. These represent classic examples of cytochrome P450-drug interactions that can lead to unwanted and unexpected clinical problems.

Regulation of cytochrome P450

The regulation of cytochrome P450 genes has also come under scrutiny lately. Research on this issue dates to the early 1950's when some biochemists showed that some of the enzymes could be induced. In particular, certain chemicals, including many drugs, ethanol, certain food substances and cigarettes smoke act to induce or suppress the activity of the genes. Moreover, some chemicals will only induce certain sets of cytochrome P450 enzymes. Curiously, there does not appear to be a tight link between the ability of a chemical to function as an inducer and its identity as a substrate. The regulation of the cytochrome P450 genes also appears to be related to natural physiological processes. For example, some of the cytochrome P450 systems in the rat appear to be controlled by sex hormones. As a result, the cytochrome P450 enzymes may function at different levels in male and female rodents. Other cytochrome P450 systems vary in their activity during certain stages of an animal's life-cycle, especially during fetal development. The regulation of one particular enzyme cytochrome P4501A1, has received considerable attention. The enzyme is of special interest because some investigators believe that its activity may be linked to lung cancer. In particular, those individuals with a highly inducible form of the enzyme seems to be more susceptible to the formation of tumors^{38,39}.

The series of steps by which cytochrome P4501A1 is induced offers an example of the complexity of these regu-

latory systems. The unraveling of the mechanism began with the discovery that dioxin is one of the most potent inducers of cytochrome P4501A1. Dioxin (TCDD) is also a very strong promoter of tumors in mice. Its efficacy as a tumor promoter hinges on whether the animal has a functional receptor (the aryl hydrocarbon hydroxylase receptor or Ah receptor) for the molecule. It was found that the Ah receptor is normally bound to a heat shock protein (hsp90) in the cytoplasm. When dioxin binds to the receptor, the hsp90 is released, allowing the receptor-dioxin couple to bind another protein, the aryl hydrocarbon receptor nuclear transferase (ARNT) molecule (Fig. 4). This complex enters the cell nucleus, where it binds to a specific region of the P4501A1 gene. The region contains a specific sequence of nucleotides (the units that define the alphabet of the genetic code) known as the Xenobiotic Regulatory Element (XRE). (Other proteins may also be involved in the binding of the complex to DNA). In a manner not yet fully understood, the protein complex then permits other proteins to reach the promoter region of the gene. This allows the synthesis of the messenger RNA (mRNA) that is the template for the synthesis of the cytochrome P4501A1 enzyme. In contrast to P4501A, much less is known about the mechanism of regulation of P4501A2, a closely related isoform. Although the latter is strongly induced by polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, suggesting a role for the Ah receptor, the 1A2 gene lacks XREs, which functions as transcriptional enhancer in the proximal 5' flanking region. Indeed the 20-40 fold in-

crease in the level of 1A2 mRNA found after treatment of cells or animals with various PAHs has been found to be mediated for the most part post-transcriptionally⁴⁰⁻⁴², apparently through enhanced stability and intranuclear processing of the 1A2 mRNA precursors⁴³. Interestingly, the Ah receptor appears to be involved in this post-transcriptional process.

mRNA stabilization as a mechanism of induction is found with several other P450s, including the alcohol-inducible cytochrome, P4502E1. In fact, this isoform is subject to multiple modes of regulation. Although diabetes and fasting produce up to a 10-fold elevation in 2E1 mRNA, the increase with diabetes results from mRNA stabilization⁴⁴, whereas the increase following fasting^{45,46} results from an increase in gene transcription⁴⁷. Furthermore, chemical inducers of the cytochrome act predominantly to stabilize the protein. The mechanism of this stabilization appears to be through ligand-mediated protection from phosphorylation, which otherwise leads to denaturation and degradation⁴⁸. The presence of phosphorylation sites on other P450s and the ability to stabilize other P450s suggest that this may be an important mechanism of P450 regulation.

Conclusions

Cytochrome P450 system plays a significant role in the human health and disease. Different cytochromes P450 are responsible for generation of essential steroid hormones, the regulation of blood levels of therapeutic agents, the removal of unwanted chemicals that would accumulate because of their lipophilicity, and the generation of potentially toxic metabolites that may cause acute cell injury or damage to genetic material leading to production of tumors. They produce important biological mediators and decrease plasma levels of drugs.

Cytochrome P450s metabolize a variety of lipophilic compounds of endogenous or exogenous origin. The enzymes may catalyze simple hydroxylation of the carbon atom of a methyl group, insertion of a hydroxyl group into a methylene carbon of an alkane, hydroxylation of an aromatic ring to form a phenol, or addition of an oxygen atom across a double bond to form an epoxide.

In a number of cases, the cytochrome P450 system is responsible for generation of the ultimate carcinogen. Formation of toxic compounds by the cytochrome P450 system, however, does not mean that cell damage or cancer will occur, because many other factors determine whether or not the toxic metabolite will cause cell injury. These include the involvement of detoxification enzyme systems, the status of the immune system, nutritional state, genetic predisposition and environmental factors.

A proper understanding of these enzymes is important

Fig. 4. Regulation of cytochrome P450 synthesis.

in applied fields relating to the metabolism of drugs, carcinogens, pesticides, steroids, toxins and vitamins. The possibilities for the applied use of cytochrome P450 enzymes should continue to grow.

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